

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL, SPECTRAL AND BIOLOGICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (3)*

Compd. no.	M p. °C	M ⁺	$\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) cm^{-1}	$\lambda_{\max}$ (log ϵ) nm	Yield %	% Antifeedant activity
3a	248	398	1 635 (C=N) 3 320 (NH)	225 (4.14) 274 (4.45) 330 (4.11)	75	49.6
b	247	466	1 608 (C=N) 3 320 (NH)	208 (4.66) 276 (4.54) 322 (4.24)	70	90.7
c	242	466	1 610 (C=N) 3 315 (NH)	218 (4.28) 266 (4.42) 325 (4.00)	68	23.8
d	230	458	1 610 (C=N) 3 320 (NH)	224 (4.56) 276 (4.61) 326 (4.30)	70	85.4
e	272	534	1 610 (C=N) 3 315 (NH)	220 (4.23) 275 (4.38) 328 (3.94)	65	94.7
f	220	518	1 610 (C=N) 3 300 (NH)	225 (4.50) 276 (4.60) 326 (4.22)	62	24.9
g	218	486	1 610 (C=N) 3 312 (NH)	203 (4.69) 270 (4.48) 330 (4.10)	67	Nil

*All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

graphy over silica gel (200 mesh). Benzene-chloroform (8 : 2, v/v) eluates on concentration afforded **2**. It gave deep red colouration with concentrated H₂SO₄ and reddish brown colouration with ethanolic FeCl₃.

4,6-Bis[4',5'-dihydro-5'-aryl pyrazol-3'-yl]resorcinols (3a-g). *General procedure*: Ethanolic solution of 2,4-bis-cinnamoylresorcinol (0.005 mol) was refluxed with 95% hydrazine hydrate (2 ml) and glacial acetic acid (few drops) for 4-6 h. Ethanol was then removed under reduced pressure and the resulting mixture was poured into ice-water. The solid separated was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from alcohol (Table 1). The compounds gave blue colouration in Lassigne's test for nitrogen.

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Synthesis of 3-Arylidine-2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-4-aryl-1,5-benzodiazepines

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DIAZEPINE derivatives have a wide therapeutic activity^{1,2}. With a view to get better therapeutic agents, we have synthesised several new 3-arylidine-2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-4-aryl-1,5-benzodiazepines (**3**) (Table 1) by the condensation of 2'-hydroxy-2-

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Sl. no.	Ar	Yield %	M p. °C
R = Phenyl			
1.	C ₆ H ₅	56	128
2.	2-Cl C ₆ H ₄	75	120
3.	3-Pyridyl	48	215
4.	<i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ -N-C ₆ H ₄	62	114
5.	2-Furyl	45	202
6.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	65	210
7.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	50	164
8.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	40	117

(Table 1 contd.)

R = <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl			
9.	C ₆ H ₅	50	118-19
10.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	50	115
11.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	50	125
12.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	54	96
13.	3 Pyridyl	51	85
14.	2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	55	89
15.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	60	100
R = <i>p</i> -Methylphenyl			
17.	C ₆ H ₅	41	159-60
18.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	40	81-82
19.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	39	136
20.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	68	170
21.	2-Furyl	50	181
22.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	40	97
23.	<i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ -N-C ₆ H ₄	43	127
R = 2-Furyl			
24.	C ₆ H ₅	38	104
25.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	42	142
26.	2-Furyl	49	140
27.	2-Pyridyl	37	159
28.	4-Pyridyl	40	157d
29.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	41	129
30.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	40	87
R = 2-Chlorophenyl			
31.	C ₆ H ₅	50	129d
32.	<i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ -N-C ₆ H ₄	30	123
33.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	30	95
34.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	45	85
35.	2-Furyl	40	183d
36.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	50	167
37.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	30	91
R = 4-Chlorophenyl			
38.	2-Pyridyl	30	220
39.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₅	35	155
40.	2-Thionyl	35	160
41.	C ₆ H ₅	39	124
42.	2-Furyl	30	190
43.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	42	225
44.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	42	150

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

aroyl-3-arylacrylophenones (1) with *o*-phenylenediamine (2) in boiling ethanolic medium in presence of a little glacial acetic acid (Scheme 1).

Scheme_1

Experimental

The 2'-hydroxy-2-aroyl-3-arylacrylophenones (1) were prepared by the known procedure³.

3-Benzylidene-2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-4-phenyl-1,5-benzodiazepine (3). Typical procedure: A mixture of 2'-hydroxy-2-benzoyl-3-phenylacrylophenone (2 g), *o*-phenylenediamine (0.64 g), ethanol (25 ml) and glacial acetic acid (0.5 ml) was refluxed for 12 h. The solvent was then removed and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (56%), m.p. 128° (Found: C, 83.8; H, 4.9; N, 6.9. C₂₈H₂₀N₂O requires: C, 84.0; H, 5.0; N, 7.0%); its alcoholic solution gave a violet colouration with concentrated HCl indicating the diazepine structure; $\nu_{\max}$ 1590 (C=N), 1340 (C-N) and 1650 cm⁻¹ (C=C).

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Synthesis and Biological Studies of some Imidazolones

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IMIDAZOLONES show diverse biological properties¹. We report here the synthesis and biological activities of some imidazolones² (1) obtained by the condensation of 2-phenyl-4-(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxybenzylidene)oxazol-5-one with sulphonamides. The imidazolones (1a-j; Table 1) showed appropriate uv and ir spectral data.